

Stereospecific Addition of Mercuric Acetate to Strained Norbornene Systems

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The stereochemistry of the addition of mercuric acetate to the olefinic bond in some Diels-Alder adducts having norbornene moiety has been shown to be *exo-cis* from the study of their pmr spectra. The magnitude of $J_{5,6}$ in the resulting addition products (4-6) is of the order of 6.5-7 Hz and $J_{1,2}$ is absent. The small value of $J_{1,6}$ observed in the addition products has been attributed to the structural distortion caused by the large HgCl group.

OXYMERCURATION is of immense synthetic importance^{1,2} as the addition products are readily obtained in high yield and these can be transformed into other products by demercuration³. The stereochemistry of the reaction has drawn much attention. Acyclic and monocyclic olefins undergo stereospecific *trans*-addition. The *trans*-addition to cyclohexene has been demonstrated by X-ray⁴, nmr⁵ and ir studies. Some olefinic systems behave differently and have been found to undergo *cis*-addition^{6,7}. The *endo*- and *exo*-dicyclopentadienes^{8,9} add mercuric salts in *exo-cis*-orientation at the 5,6-double bond. The present study deals with some new Diels-Alder adducts (1-3) having the norbornene moiety which have been subjected for the first time to oxymercuration. The stereochemistry of the addition products (4-6) has been demonstrated with the help of pmr spectroscopy. This system has been considered interesting as it incorporates three olefinic systems of different nature, the cage-olefinic systems at C-5 and C-6, the bridge between C-7 and C-8 with aryl substituents and the olefinic bond of the dienophile moiety. Further, it has been considered to investigate the potentiality of the addition products as a 'probe' in the configurational assignments of the Diels-Alder adducts (1-3).

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Results and Discussion

Oxymercuration of 6,6-diphenylfulvene-*p*-benzoquinone adduct (1) with mercuric acetate in absolute

methanol yielded the addition product (4). Pmr spectra of the compound 4 exhibited multiplets (4H) at δ 2.32–2.94 for H-1, H-2, H-3 and H-4, a doublet at δ 3.0 (1H, J 7Hz and 2.5Hz) for H-6, a doublet at δ 5.1 (1H, J 7Hz) for H-5, a singlet (3H) at δ 3.48 for methoxy protons, an AB quartet (2H, J 10Hz) at δ 6.65 for the olefinic protons of dienophile moiety along with a multiplet at δ 7.28–8.06 for aromatic protons (10H). Based on coupling constant Anet⁹ investigated the stereochemistry of bornane-2,3-diol. The coupling constant $J_{2,3}$ 7.7 and 8.9Hz were assigned for *cis-exo-exo* and *endo-endo* diols respectively, whereas $J_{2,3}$ 2.2Hz was attributed for *trans*-diol. Further, it was observed by Anet⁹ that in bornane diol $J_{3,4} \approx 0$ when the hydroxyl group occupies an *exo* position and $H J_{3,4} \approx 4$ Hz when the hydroxyl group is in *endo* position. The coupling constant of the doublet (7Hz) in the product 4 is of the similar order as that reported for the *exo-cis* configuration of bornane-2,3-diol⁹ supported the *exo-cis* geometry of HgCl and OCH₃ group. The absence of $J_{4,5}$ coupling further demonstrated that the methoxy group occupies an *exo* position in consistent with Anet's observation. The presence of second coupling (2.5Hz) for H-6 was attributed to the structural distortion caused by the mercury atom. The appearance of an AB quartet for the olefinic protons indicated that one of the protons has been influenced by HgCl group, which further demonstrated the *endo* nature of the Diels–Alder adduct. In case of an *exo* configuration the olefinic protons would have remained unaffected. The olefinic bridge (C-7) of the compound did not undergo electrophilic addition due to steric effect. Electrophilic addition of mercuric acetate (one mole) to the olefinic bond between C-5 and C-6 will be considered more facile as compared with the addition to the olefinic bond of the dienophile moiety which is being controlled by the availability of π -electron density. The π -electron density of the olefinic bond of the dienophile moiety is diluted by resonance due to the adjacent carbonyl groups and hence the developing carbonium ion will be destabilised.

The oxymercured product (5) showed multiplets at δ 2.22–3.23 (5H) for H-1 to H-4 and H-6, a singlet at δ 3.46 for methoxy protons, a doublet (1H, J 6.5Hz) at 5.02 for H-5 along with a multiplet at δ 7.32–8.08 for aromatic protons (14H). The coupling constant magnitude 6.5Hz for H-5 suggested the addition to be *exo-cis* as has been explained in case of the compound 4. Due to the overlapping of other resonances H-6 splitting was not clear. The appearance of the methoxy group at δ 3.46 in the compound 5 further demonstrated its *exo*-orientation as in case of *endo*-orientation it would have been influenced by the benzene ring of the cage-moiety. Molecular models also supported the *exo-cis* geometry of HgCl and OCH₃ group.

Pmr spectra of compound 6 exhibited two singlets each of 3H intensity at δ 2.20 and 2.28 for acetoxy protons, a singlet (3H) for methoxy protons at δ

2.78, a doublet doublet (1H, J 7Hz and 3Hz) at δ 3.0 for H-6, a multiplet (2H) at δ 3.83 for H-1 and H-4, a doublet (1H, J 7Hz) at δ 5.1 for H-5 along with multiplets (12H) at δ 7.42–7.83 for aromatic protons. The coupling constant J 7Hz for H-5 and H-6 suggested the *cis*-addition. Moreover, the absence of coupling constant between H-4 and H-5 indicated the methoxy group being in *exo*-orientation. The second coupling constant (J 3Hz) for H-6 may likely to be $J_{1,6}$ which would result from the distortion of the ring by the mercury as suggested by Anderson and Henry⁶ while studying the stereochemistry of the oxymercured product of the norbornene. Molecular model of compound 6 suggested the interaction between the methoxy group and the acetoxy group adjacent to position-3, therefore the methoxy protons would fall in the shielding zone of the HgCl and appears at δ 2.78. The appearance of acetoxy protons as two singlets was due to dissimilarity of the *endo* protons at C-5 and C-6.

Experimental

Pmr spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ using TMS as the internal standard on a Varian-A-60D spectrometer at 45°. Ir spectra were recorded in nujol mull on a Perkin–Elmer 257 spectrophotometer and were found to be characteristic of the compounds. The carbon and hydrogen elemental analyses of the compounds were within acceptable experimental limits.

6,6-Diphenylfulvene-*p*-benzoquinone(endo) adduct (1): 6,6-Diphenylfulvene and *p*-benzoquinone in equimolar proportion in dry benzene were refluxed for about 90 min. The benzene was removed under reduced pressure and the product was recrystallised from ethanol m.p. 98–9° (lit.¹⁰ 99°) (Found: C, 85.09; H, 5.41. C₂₄H₁₈O₂ requires; C, 85.21; H, 5.33%); δ 3.62 (2H, m, H-2 and H-3), 3.97 (2H, m, H-1 and H-4), 6.32 (2H, t, H-5 and H-6), 6.64 (2H, s, olefinic protons of dienophile moiety) and 7.24 (10H, m, aromatic protons).

6,6-Diphenylfulvene-1,4-naphthoquinone adduct (2): It was prepared by refluxing 6,6-diphenylfulvene and 1,4-naphthoquinone in equimolar proportion in dry benzene for 6 h. Benzene was removed under reduced pressure and the product was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 105–07° (Found: C, 86.87; H, 5.22. C₂₈H₂₀O₂ requires: C, 86.59; H, 5.16%); δ 3.5–3.72 (4H, m, H-1 to H-4), 6.06 (2H, t, H-5 and H-6), 7.41 (14H, m, aromatic protons).

Preparation of compound 3: Diels–Alder adduct of 6,6-diphenylfulvene-*p*-benzoquinone (1) was refluxed in excess acetic anhydride for ~4 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into ice-cold water to give a solid material which on recrystallisation from ethanol yielded crystals of 3, m.p. 115–16° (Found: C, 79.91; H, 5.26. C₂₈H₂₂O₄ requires: C, 79.62; H, 5.21%); δ 2.31

(6H, s, acetyl protons), 3.85 (2H, m, H-1 and H-4), 6.82 (2H, t, H-5 and H-6) and 7.52 (12 H, m, aromatic protons).

Preparation of mercurial derivatives (4-6): The mercuric acetate in dry methanol was added to the stirred solution of an equimolar amount of the adduct (1, 2 and 3) over a period of 12 h to complete the reaction. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was treated with excess sodium chloride. The precipitate was filtered and washed with water. The product was recrystallised from benzene-dichloromethane mixture: **4**, m.p. 110-11° (Found: C, 49.80; H, 3.53; $C_{25}H_{21}O_3$ HgCl requires: C, 49.58; H, 3.47%); **5**, m.p. 160-61° (Found: C, 52.92; H, 3.58; $C_{29}H_{25}O_3$ HgCl requires: C, 53.13; H, 3.51%); **6**, m.p. 191-92° (Found: C, 50.68; H, 3.71; $C_{29}H_{25}O_3$ HgCl requires: C, 50.50; H, 3.63%).

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